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Two new species of the genus *Troglamaurops* Ganglbauer 1903 (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae: Amauropini) from Southern Dinarides

DRAGAN PAVIĆEVIĆ¹, ROMAN OZIMEC², CLAUDE BESUCHET†, GIULIO CUCCODORO³

¹Krunska 15, 11 000 Belgrade, Serbia, Serbian Biospeleological Society, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 2, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia, e-mail: dragan.pavicevic@hotmail.com

²ADIPA: Society for Croatian Natural History Diversity Research & Conservation, Orehovečki ogranak 37, 10040 Zagreb, Croatia, e-mail: roman.ozimec@adipa.hr

†(1930–2020)

³Muséum d'histoire naturelle, Geneva, Switzerland, e-mail: giulio.cuccodoro@ville-ge.ch

SUMMARY. Two new species of the genus *Troglamaurops*: *T. korkyrae* sp. n. and *T. travuniae* sp. n. from Southern Dalmatia and East Hercegovina are described, illustrated and compared with related species. Morphological characters of the new species are discussed, as well as their chorology and ecology preferences. Aedeagi of five so far known *Troglamaurops* species are presented with drawings. The distribution of the genus is shown on the map.

KEYWORDS: Bosnia and Hercegovina, caves, Croatia, taxonomy, troglobiont.

INTRODUCTION

The members of *Troglamaurops* Ganglbauer, 1903, are small sized, depigmented, eyeless Amauropini characterized by slim body and very elongated legs and antennae. They inhabit subterranean habitats in South Dinarides, Croatia and Hercegovina, and are exclusively troglobionts.

So far, *Troglamaurops* comprises three species: *T. leptoderinus* (Reitter, 1901) and *T. scheibeli* Müller, 1944 from South Dalmatia, and *T. ganglbaueri* Winkler, 1925 from the lower course of the river Neretva in Hercegovina (Nonveiller & Pavićević 2008; Hlavač et al. 2008, 2017).

Specimens of *Troglamaurops* are very rare in collections. It is necessary to make significant research efforts to find them, which consists notably in spending hours in caves looking for optimal microhabitats. So, it is not surprising that *T. leptoderinus* was described based on one male, *T. ganglbaueri* based on one female, and *T. scheibeli* based on 4 specimens only, which is not surprising. Since the de-

scription of the latter species by Müller (1944), no taxonomic work on this genus was published for 90 years. From the first finding on 13.05.1900 (Reitter 1901) till the last finding mentioned in this article (21.09.2023), a nearly 50 specimens have been found over a period of more than 120 years, over 30 of them collected in the last 25 years. Thanks to these findings, we provide the description of two new species of *Troglamaurops*, and present more comprehensive information on the ecology and distribution of the members of the genus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Specimens of *Troglamaurops* were searched in caves by visual inspection of the walls, and under stones on the floor. Traps with attractants did not produce results. Specimens found were collected using soft tweezers and placed directly in vials containing 70% ethanol.

During research, basic cave microclimate is measured: air temperature, substrate temperature, relative air humidity, optionally also content of CO₂ in air. Also cave habitats are recognized, according to Croatian National habitat classification, ver. 5.0. According to the conditions in the finding micro localities, and specimens' activity, the found specimens were macro-photographed *in situ*, using several camera models, mostly CANON EOS 4000 with a close-up objective, and several generations of OLYMPUS MJU TOUGHT.

For the laboratory study of specimens, LEICA MZ 16 and WILD M 8 ZOOM stereomicroscope are used, as well as CARL ZEISS AXIOSCOPE 40 microscope. Following measurement are performed: total body length, head length, maximum head width, antennal length, pronotal length, pronotal width, elytral length, elytral width.

Male genitalia were dissected, put for several hours in Caryophylli aetheroleum solution (Clove oil), then mounted in Canada balsam on plastic transparent slides pinned under the dry mounted specimens. The line drawings of aedeagi were made by C. Besuchet†, and inked by G. Cuccodoro. The drawings of habitus were made by Momčilo Popović. The photos of specimens *in situ* were taken by R. Ozimec.

Collection depository is given for each specimen, with inventory number for the holotypes. Also, for all five species their exact type locality is given.

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AL antennal length

BA Bosnia and Hercegovina

CDP private collection of Dragan Pavićević, Belgrade (Serbia)

EL elytral length (as linear distance measured along the suture from the elytral base to the apex)

EW maximum width of elytra

HL head length: measured from the anterior margin of the clypeus to the neck constriction

HR Croatia

HW maximum width of head

LT Locus typicus

MHNG Muséum d'histoire naturelle, Geneva, Switzerland

NHGMV Natural-history department of State Museum of Varaždin city (GMV) (Croatia)

NHMZ Natural-history Museum in Zagreb Collection (Croatia)

PL pronotal length

PW maximum pronotal width

RH Relative humidity of the air

ROC Roman Ozimec Collection, Varaždin, part of NHGMV (Croatia)

Ta Temperature of air

TL total body length: measured from the apex of mandibles to the apex of last tergite

Ts Temperature of substrate

TAXONOMY

Troglamaurops korkyrae sp. n. (Figs 1, 2, 6, 3A)

HOLOTYPE: male; HR, Dalmatia, Island Korčula, Račišće, špilja Samograd cave; 18.03.2010; leg. R. Ozimec; Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr GMV 105125 (Fig. 1).

PARATYPES: (3 males, 8 females): 1 male, same locality, 04.06.2000, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 female, same locality, 18.03.2010; leg. R. Ozimec; 1 male, 5 females, same locality, 16.04.2011, leg. I. Njunjić; 1 female, HR, Dalmatia, Island Korčula, Korčula, špilja Pišurka cave, 23.04.2004, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 female, same locality, 26.12.2009, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 male, same locality, 12.08.2011, leg. R. Ozimec (Coll. CDP, MHNG, ROC).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE

Small sized (TL 2.20 mm) (Figs 1, 2), shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with very dense and long pubescence. Head (HL 0.45 mm, HW 0.38 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum; frontal lobe transverse with widely rounded anterior margin; eyeless, without indication of ocular carinae; genae rounded, narrowed posteriorly, with long and erected setae; frons with deep depression; vertexal foveae well-defined; occipital carina present but weak and short, not reaching vertexal foveae. Maxillary palpi 0.20 mm long, palpomere III as long as palponeres I and II. Antennae (AL 1.37 mm) relatively short, all antennomeres elongate; scape subcylindrical: 0.13/0.07; pedicel: 0.12/0.05; III: 0.10/0.03; IV: 0.10/0.03; V: 0.15/0.03; VI: 0.10/0.03; VII: 0.12/0.03; VIII: 0.09/0.03; IX: 0.11/0.04; X: 0.10/0.05; XI: 0.25/0.08. Pronotum (PL 0.43 mm, PW 0.38 mm) longer than wide, widest behind middle, shorter than head, barrel-shaped; median fovea shallow and elongated; lateral foveae well-defined, deep. Elytra (EL 0.68 mm, EW 0.58 mm) longer than wide. Legs long and slender. Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite, slightly wider than long (0.57/0.60), with shallow depression, external stria fused with tergal margin, internal stria very short, distance between them about 0.20 mm. Aedeagus 0.26 mm long (Fig. 3A).

Fig. 1. *Troglamaurops korkyrae* sp. n., holotype *in situ*, Špilja Samograd cave, 18.03.2010.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Troglamaurops korkyrae* sp. n. can be distinguished from close related *T. ganglbaueri* Winkler, 1925 through wider head, the antennomere VIII clearly shorter than IX., longer and wider pronotum and elytra, different shape of aedeagus.

ETYMOLOGY

After oldest Greek name for Korčula island - Korkyra Melaina (lat. Corcyra Nigra). According to the female gender, possessive adjective is - korkyrae.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY

Basic data	Samograd LT: Cave on 165m asl, depth -45 m, length 120 m, Fig. 4. Pišurka: Cave on 47 m asl, depth -31 m, length 74 m, Map on Fig. 5.
Microclimate	Samograd LT: Ta = 13.5-15.7 °C; Ts = 13.2-15.0 °C; RH: 93-100%. Pišurka: Ta = 15.4-15.7 °C; Ts = 14.8-15.0 °C; RH: 98-100%.
Basic habitats	Samograd LT: Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglobitic invertebrates. Pišurka: same as Samograd.
LT for taxa	Samograd (2): Araneae: <i>Lepthyphantes korculensis</i> F. Miller, 1978 = syn. of <i>Palliduphantes istrianus</i> (Kulczyński, 1914); Coleoptera: <i>Nonveillera romani</i> Pavičević & Besuchet, 2003. Pišurka (9): Gastropoda: <i>Spelaeoconcha paganettii paganettii</i> Sturany, 1901; Araneae: <i>Barusia korculana</i> (Kratohvil & Miller, 1939), <i>Folkia haasi</i> (Reimoser, 1929), <i>Typhlonyphia reimoseri reimoseri</i> Kratochvil, 1936; Isopoda: <i>Aegonethes cervinus</i> (Verhoeff, 1931), <i>Alpioniscus haasi</i> (Verhoeff, 1931); Coleoptera: <i>Dalmatiola curzolenis</i> (Ganglbauer, 1902), <i>Speonesiotes paganettii</i> (Ganglbauer, 1902); Diptera: <i>Bradysia dalmatina</i> (Lengersdorf, 1937).
Other taxa in LT	After Ozimec, 2004; add.: Gastropoda: <i>Spelaeoconcha paganettii paganettii</i> Sturany, 1901; Araneae: <i>Barusia korculana</i> (Kratohvil & Miller, 1939), <i>Folkia haasi</i> (Reimoser, 1929), <i>Typhlonyphia reimoseri reimoseri</i> Kratochvil, 1936; Isopoda: <i>Aegonethes cervinus</i> (Verhoeff, 1931), <i>Alpioniscus haasi</i> (Verhoeff, 1931); Chilopoda: <i>Eupolybothrus</i> sp.; Palpigradi: <i>Eukoenenia</i> sp.; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp., <i>Neobisium</i> sp.; Diplura: <i>Plusiocampa (Stygocampa)</i> sp., <i>Japyx</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Dalmatiola curzolenis</i> (Ganglbauer, 1902), <i>Speonesiotes paganettii</i> (Ganglbauer, 1902); <i>Laemostenus cavicola erberi</i> (Schaufuss, 1863); Orthoptera: <i>Dolichopoda araneiformis</i> Burmeister, 1838, <i>Troglophilus cavicola</i> Kollar, 1833.

Fig. 2. *Troglamaurops korkyrae* sp. n., habitus, holotype, scale bar 1 mm.

Fig. 3. Aedeagi, dorsal view. **A**, *Troglamaurops korkyrae* sp. n.; **B**, *T. travunia* sp. n.; **C**, *T. ganglbaueri* Winkler 1925; **D**, *T. leptoderinus* (Reitter, 1901); **E**, *T. scheibeli* (Müller, 1944).

So far known only from Samograd and Pišurka caves, both located on Island Korčula, Dalmatia, HR (Fig. 6). Is an endemic species of the Korčula island.

Fig. 4. Map of Špilja Samograd cave, after Ozimec, 2004.

Fig. 5. Map of Špilja Pišurka cave, after Ozimec & Pavlek, 2005.

Fig. 6. Distribution of *Troglamaurops* species in south Dalmatia and East Hercegovina.

Troglamaurops travuniae sp. n. (Figs 3B, 6-8)

HOLOTYPE: male, BA, Federation of Bosnia and Hercegovina, Popovo polje, Ravno, Zavala, Vjetrenica cave, 20.08.2008, leg. R. Ozimec; Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr GMV 105128 (Fig. 7).

PARATYPE: 1 male, same location, 16.08.2004, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 female, same data as holotype (Coll. CDP, MHNG).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE

Small sized (TL 2.40 mm; female paratype: TL 2.45 mm) (Figs 7, 8), shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with very long erect setae. Head (HL 0.48 mm, HW 0.36 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum. Frontal lobe transverse with widely rounded anterior margin; eyes completely atrophied, without indication of ocular carinae; genae rounded, narrowed posteriorly, with long and erect setae; frons with two depressions; vertexal foveae well-defined; occipital carina present but not reaching vertexal foveae. Maxillary palpi 0.22 mm long, with palpomere III as long as palpomeres I and II. Antennae (AL 1.61 mm) long, all antennomeres elongate; scape subcylindrical: 0.15/0.08; pedicel: 0.14/0.05; III: 0.10/0.03; IV: 0.10/0.03; V: 0.15/0.02; VI: 0.10/0.02; VII: 0.16/0.03; VIII: 0.11/0.03; IX: 0.17/0.04; X: 0.15/0.07; XI: 0.28/0.010. Pronotum (PL 0.45 mm, PW 0.37 mm) longer than wide, widest behind middle, shorter than head; bar-

rel-shaped; median fovea shallow and elongated; lateral foveae well-defined, deep. Elytra (EL 0.75 mm, EW 0.60 mm) longer than wide. Legs long and slender. Abdomen slightly wider than elytra, first visible tergite (0.40/0.60) much wider than long, with shallow depression, external stria fused with tergal margin, internal stria very short, distance between them about 0.20 mm. Aedeagus 0.26 mm long (Fig. 3B).

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Troglamaurops travuniae* sp. n. can be distinguished from close related *T. ganglbaueri* Winkler, 1925 through longer body, longer and wider head, longer antennae, longer and wider pronotum and elytra and different shape of aedeagus.

ETYMOLOGY

After Travunia (lat. Tribunia), a historical area that stretched along the Adriatic coast between Kotor and Dubrovnik, and inland on the part of today's East Herzegovina and Montenegro. According to the female gender of this region, possessive adjective is *travuniae*.

Fig. 7. *Troglamaurops travuniae* sp. n., holotype *in situ*, pećina Vjetrenica cave, 20.08.2008.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY

Basic data	Complex cave system with entrance on 268 m asl, depth -43,6 m, length 7.323,9 m, surface ca 62.654 m ² , volume ca 365.000 m ³ ; Map in Fig. 9.
Microclimate	Ta = 12.0 °C; Ts = 11.8 °C; RH: 98-100%.
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	After Ozimec et al., 2021 (41 taxa), here only Coleoptera (6): <i>Adriaphaenops pretneri</i> Scheibel, 1935, <i>Aphaenopsis apfelbecki</i> Ganglbauer, 1891, <i>Scotoplanetes arenstorffianus</i> Absolon, 1913, <i>Graciliella apfelbecki apfelbecki</i> (Müller, 1910), <i>Hadesia vasiceki</i> (J. Müller, 1911), <i>Nauticicella stygivaga</i> Moravec et Mlejnek, 2002.
Other taxa	After Ozimec et al., 2021 (321 taxa), here only Coleoptera (10): <i>Lae-mostenus (Antisphodrus) cavicola</i> (Schaum, 1858), <i>Neotrechus dalmatinus</i> (Miller, 1861), <i>Neotrechus suturalis otiosus</i> (Obenberger, 1917), <i>Anthroherpon primitivum</i> (Absolon, 1913), <i>Speonesiotes (S.) narentinus latitarsus</i> (Apfelbeck, 1919), <i>Speonesiotes (S.) schweitzeri</i> Jeannel 1941, <i>Quedius mesomelinus kraussi</i> Penecke, 1904, <i>Bryaxis scapularis</i> (Reitter, 1881), <i>Nonveilleria</i> sp., <i>Troglamaurops ganglbaueri</i> (Winkler, 1925).

DISTRIBUTION

Known only from pećina Vjetrenica cave, Zavala, Popovo polje, East Hercegovina, Federation of Bosnia and Hercegovina, BA. Can be defined as an endemic species for Vjetrenica cave, Popovo polje and Bosnia and Hercegovina (Fig. 6).

ADDITIONAL MATERIAL RESEARCHED

Troglamaurops ganglbaueri Winkler, 1925 (Figs 3C, 6)

LT: Markova pećina cave, Njavre, Hrasno, Neum, BA

MATERIAL EXAMINED: 1 male, 1 female, 15.11.2014, leg. R. Ozimec, Špilja iznad Kopren Dola cave, Vidonje, Zažablje, Metković, HR; 1 female, 15.10.2011., leg. R. Ozimec, Vranja peć cave, Točionik, Dubrovačko primorje, HR; 1 female, 25.08.2014., leg. G. Rujak, same locality; 1 male, 1 female, 25.09.2014., leg. R. Ozimec, same locality; 1 female, Žira pećina cave, Turkovići, Popovo Polje, Hercegovina, BA; 1 female, 16.08.2004. leg. R. Ozimec; same locality but 16.08.1999-

Fig. 8. *Troglamaurops travuniae* sp. n., habitus, holotype, scale bar 1 mm.

Fig. 9. Pećina Vjetrenica cave map, after Ozimec et al., 2021.

10.06.2000, 2 females, leg. R. Mlejnek; same locality 21.10.2000, 1 male, leg. J. Lakota; Pećina Vjetrenica cave, Zavala, Ravno, Popovo polje, Hercegovina. (Coll. CDP, ROC).

DISTRIBUTION

Spread over a wider area of southern Dalmatia and East Hercegovina (Fig. 6).

Troglamaurops leptoderinus (Reitter, 1901) (Figs 3D, 6, 10)

LT: Gorska jama cave, Janjina, Pelješac, HR

MATERIAL EXAMINED: 1 female, Nakovana špilja cave, Viganj, Orebić, Pelješac, HR, 25.09.2009., leg. R. Ozimec; 1 male, Pećina kod Janjine cave, Pelješac, HR, leg. S. Svirčev (Coll. CDP, ROC); 1 male, Sabioncelo Höhlen (Pelješac caves), collector unknown; 1 female, Dalmatia, collector V. Apfelbeck (MNHG).

DISTRIBUTION

So far known only from two speleological objects on Pelješac peninsula (Fig. 6).

Troglamaurops scheibeli (Müller, 1944) (Figs 3E, 6)

LT: Špilja od Punta cave, Močići, Čilipi, Konavle, HR

MATERIAL EXAMINED: 2 males, 1 female, Špilja od Punta cave, Cavtat, HR, 10. 1951, leg. Stanko Karaman (Coll. CDP)

DISTRIBUTION

So far known only from Špilja od Punta cave, Cavtat in Konavle (South Dalmatia) (Fig. 6).

DISCUSSION

Troglamaurops now comprises 5 species: 4 distributed in South Dalmatia (Croatia), 1 in East Hercegovina (Bosnia and Hercegovina), and 1 in both territories (Fig. 6).

We have discovered sympatry of two *Troglamaurops* species in the Vjetrenica cave (Zavala, Popovo polje, East Hercegovina) where *T. ganglbaueri* and *T. travuniae*

Fig. 10. *Troglamaurops leptoderinus* (Reitter, 1901), *in situ*, Nakovana špilja cave, 25.09.2009.

sp. n. occurs. It is interesting to notice that Müller (1944: 99) noted that he had examined four specimens of *T. ganglbaueri* from Vjetrenica cave in Hercegovina and noticed that only one specimen had narrow and prolonged head like the typical *T. ganglbaueri*, while the other three specimens had wider heads. He concluded that these differences were due to intraspecific variability of the species. However, if he had studied their aedeagi he would have observed notable differences between specimens with narrow and wider heads from the Vjetrenica cave. Our study of a few specimens of *T. ganglbaueri* from Vjetrenica cave showed that they had slightly wider head, but never as wide as in *T. travuniae* sp. n. Specimens of *T. ganglbaueri* from the caves and pits from the environ of Metković (Vidanje) and Točionik, both in Croatia, are always smaller, with narrow head and slender body. We had an opportunity to study small series of *T. ganglbaueri* specimens collected in Žira cave in Popovo Polje and we have found that they are very similar to specimens from the nearby cave Vjetrenica. The study of the aedeagi of all examined *T. ganglbaueri* specimens showed that they had always the

same shape and size (Fig. 3C). *Troglamaurops ganglbaueri* was recorded also from the Gabrovica cave near Grebci (Müller 1944). We present here that at least two *Troglamaurops* species do occur in this area, and that in some of the caves they are even sympatric. Thus, which of the two species, *ganglbaueri* or *travuniae* sp. n., really inhabit the cave Gabrovica remains unclear.

Troglamaurops leptoderinus was known only from its type locality, an unspecified cave near Janjina, Pelješac (Müller 1944). One of the coauthors (R.O.) discovered this species in Nakovana špilja cave, Viganj, Orebić, Pelješac peninsula, the second and only precisely located site. This very slender species with very elongated body and appendages has a peculiar shape of its aedeagus (Fig. 3D). *Troglamaurops scheibeli*, was reliably known only from its type locality, cave Punta Spila near Cavtat (Müller 1944). It is more robust species with much longer antennae than *T. leptoderinus*.

In the same region of Konavle representatives of two exclusively troglobitic psephenid genera were found, *Troglamaurops* (*T. scheibeli*) and *Seracamaurops* (*S. kadmei*). *Troglamaurops scheibeli* (Müller, 1944) is distributed in lower Konavle, near the Adriatic sea, in moderate cave habitats, while *Seracamaurops kadmei* Pavićević & Ozimec, 2013 is present in upper Konavle (Sniježnica Mt.) in colder cave habitats at significantly higher altitudes.

According to the Red book of Croatian cave dwelling fauna (Ozimec et al. 2009), both *Troglamaurops leptoderinus* (Reitter, 1901) and *Troglamaurops scheibeli* (J. Müller, 1944), were stated as critically endangered – CR, criteria B1ab(iii)+2ab(iii). We consider that in the future all known *Troglamaurops* taxa should fall in this category.

Our study of all representatives of the genus *Troglamaurops* showed that morphological differences between species are rather scarce and the most reliable diagnostic features are the aedeagal characters. Other characters, such as the narrow or wide head, the length of the antennae, legs, etc. may be used as a support in species identification. Single female specimens of *Troglamaurops* taxa are usually very hard to identify. Therefore, we have not study here in detail several unidentified females found in new localities for this genus. They will be object of future field researches.

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